

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Introduction to the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)

Data Curation Roadshow - Southampton
8th July 2025

<https://www.psdi.ac.uk/>

Presentation Outline

- ▶ What is PSDI
- ▶ A sample of PSDI Offerings
- ▶ Getting involved with PSDI

What is PSDI?

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

- ▶ UK funded project through the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure theme (DRI) via EPSRC
- ▶ Developed out of a community statement of need
- ▶ Lead institutions: University of Southampton and Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC)
- ▶ First launch of resources are now live!

Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure

An Integrated Data Infrastructure for the Physical Sciences

PSDI aims to accelerate research in the physical sciences by providing a data infrastructure that brings together and builds upon the various data systems researchers currently use.

www.psd.ac.uk

Drivers for PSDI: Barriers & Challenges for the Physical Sciences

Data

- ▶ Lack of access to reusable structured datasets
 - ▶ Un-FAIR Data
- ▶ Data locked away in proprietary formats
- ▶ Lack of metadata / provenance
- ▶ Cost of storing data

Technology

- ▶ Too many (and yet not enough) formats and standards
- ▶ Complexity in selecting and adhering to standards
- ▶ Lack of interoperability between software

People

- ▶ Attitude and adoption of standards and principles
- ▶ Lack of knowledge and skills around data management (need data stewards!)
- ▶ Lack of time and human resource

The Aim

PSDI will provide

A data infrastructure that
connects existing
experimental and computational facilities
within Physical Sciences and beyond

A platform for data collection, sharing, aggregation, integration and curation

Supporting analysis across experimental, simulation and reference data

Combining and enhancing existing data infrastructures

Sustaining data resources beyond lifespan of individual research projects

Diverse Pathfinders driving requirements

What can PSDI do for you?

Data Services

Data Tools

**Community
Activities**

**Access to
Data Sources**

**Guidance,
Training &
Case Studies**

**Opportunities
for
Collaboration**

Find our resources on www.psd.ac.uk!

Access to Data

Over 30 different data sources

Including:

- ▶ Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)
- ▶ Propersea (Property Prediction)
- ▶ Chemical Availability Search (ChASe)
- ▶ Chemotion
- ▶ STFC Open Data

Data Revival Service

PSDI is providing a free version of the Data Revival Software

- ▶ This can be used to scan your handwritten lab book pages and turn them into machine-readable data
- ▶ Remember: Even if you implement digital notetaking tomorrow, there will still be a considerable amount of legacy data that may require digitisation

Scan in paper
lab notebook
pages

Convert into
machine-
readable
content

Relational
links across
chemistry
data

Semantic
Search

High degree
of accuracy

Data Format Conversion Service

We have created a service to address the issue of Interoperability in the Physical Sciences

- ▶ Ultimate goal: One stop shop for data conversion – without the need to write complicated code or download and test many converters
- ▶ Provide information about conversions and potential quality issues e.g. loss of information

Extensive
Format
Support

Multiple
Converters

Seamless
Customisable
Conversion

Accessibility

Multiple
mechanisms
of use

Reproducible Scientific Workflows

- ▶ Often papers don't contain enough detail to allow simulation or analysis to be repeated
- ▶ We're developing tools to capture the full data provenance in a scientific workflow

Link data and models to results and publications

Simple for researchers!

Support multiple workflow systems

Visualise the provenance for calculations

Allow users to store their provenance archives

- ▶ Initial Focus areas: Biomolecular simulations, machine learnt interatomic potentials, muon experiments, X-Ray absorption spectroscopy

Knowledge Base

- ▶ The PSDI Knowledge Base will provide guidance for physical scientists, and those who support them, about a range of topics related to research data and PSDI technology and resources.

- ▶ A growing collection of content that can be built with the community.

Case Studies

- ▶ To supplement our guidance, we are also producing case studies to help the community, ranging from implementing new tools to curating legacy data

- ▶ If you have existing case studies or ideas for new ones please get in touch!

Training Activities

PSDI is committed to upskilling the physical sciences community, and we offer a range of training activities

- ▶ Self Paced Learning Resources
- ▶ In Person Training
 - ▶ Training Workshops
 - ▶ Skills4Scientists Intern Training
 - ▶ Machine Learning Summer Schools
- ▶ Tutorials
- ▶ Webinars

DATA PUBLISHING	
GOOD	BAD
DATA REPOSITORY	STICKY NOTE ON YOUR DOOR
INSTITUTIONAL ARCHIVE	SUPPLEMENTARY DATA
	BOTTOM OF A WELL

AI4SD
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<https://errantscience.com/>

Community

Not just about technology Channel with Publishers

Internships & Placements

Advocacy

Community
workshops & forums

Identify Skills Gaps

Research
Culture

Channel with Funders

Requirements gathering

Champions

Policy Design & Implementation

Community of
Practice

Validation of ideas

Sharing Best
Practice

Data skills
training

Provision of
guidance

Community Involvement

CaSDaR
Careers and Skills for
Data-driven Reserach

ELN Finder

InChI TRUST

WorldFAIR

CCDC
advancing structural science

BEILSTEIN INSTITUT

NFDI4@t
NFDI for Catalysis-Related Sciences

IUCr
International Union
of Crystallography

If you want to get involved with PSDI contact psdi@soton.ac.uk!

Got an idea to solve a data problem?

Speak to us!

You can reach the team through psdi@soton.ac.uk and we will connect you

Find out more about PSDI

 www.psdi.ac.uk

 PSDIUK

 @PSDI_UK

 @psdi-uk.bsky.social

 @PSDI@mstdn.science

 @PSDI_UK

 PSDI zenodo
community

Join our mailing list!

<https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/PSDI>

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Roadshow Context

How can PSDI best support
Data Curation in the Physical
Sciences?

<https://www.psd.ac.uk/>

Background

- ▶ As partners of the PSDI project, Digital Curation Centre (DCC) and Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC) are aiming to identify recommendations for **how PSDI can and should support data curation needs of UK Physical Sciences communities.**
- ▶ **Areas we want to explore:**
 - ▶ The extent to which existing guidance, tools and services support current and future data curation needs
 - ▶ Data curation requirements specific to the physical sciences that go beyond general data requirements
 - ▶ How PSDI could help address unmet needs whether through guidance, tools, training, active curation or collaboration

Current Report Outline

- ▶ **What is Data Curation?!**
 - ▶ How it fits in the research lifecycle
 - ▶ Curation vs management vs preservation
- ▶ **Roles and Responsibilities**
 - ▶ What do we need from various stakeholders? Where might stakeholders need help?
- ▶ **Community Benchmarks**
 - ▶ Expectations of e.g. CoreTrustSeal
- ▶ **Available guidelines on best practice**
 - ▶ Domain-agnostic vs domain-specific
- ▶ **Case studies in the Physical Sciences**
 - ▶ Crystallography, PSDI Pathfinders, NFDI4Chem, others
- ▶ **Interoperability and integration**
 - ▶ Importance of joined-up recording and reporting workflows and platforms
- ▶ **Community needs**
 - ▶ Drawing on community engagement at curation roadshows and other events
- ▶ **Recommendations for PSDI**
 - ▶ Guidance, tools, training, services etc.

Roadshow Outline

▶ **Presentations**

- ▶ Perspectives on data curation and publication

▶ **Exercise**

- ▶ Data Management Plans in the Physical Sciences

▶ **Breakout discussion sessions**

- ▶ What data curation means to you
- ▶ Challenges and pain points
- ▶ Roles, responsibilities and skills
- ▶ Tools, resources and training required
- ▶ How PSDI could best help

Breakout Discussions

▶ **Introductions**

- ▶ Your relationship to data curation and management

▶ **Discussion 1: Data Curation and Management**

- ▶ What is data curation? What is involved?
- ▶ How does data curation differ from / relate to data management and data preservation?
- ▶ Main challenges and pain points?

▶ **Discussion 2: Roles and Responsibilities**

- ▶ Who is responsible for data curation and data management?
- ▶ What skills and strengths do different stakeholders offer?
- ▶ Role of AI/Machine Learning?
- ▶ What limitations in knowledge, tools, guidance are hindering best practice?

▶ **Discussion 3: What could PSDI do?**

- ▶ How could PSDI support data curation and data management in physical sciences?
- ▶ What tools, resources, and training are needed?

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
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Putting the R into FAIR Data – The complexities of FAIR data and the importance of Data Stewardship in the Physical Sciences

8th July 2025

**Dr Samantha Pearman-Kanza
University of Southampton**

<https://www.psdi.ac.uk/>

Presentation Outline

- ▶ About Me
- ▶ Data Challenges
- ▶ FAIR Data & Reusability
- ▶ The Importance of Data Stewardship
- ▶ The CaSDaR Network+

With contributions from
Sharkcat

About Me

- ▶ Senior Enterprise Fellow at University of Southampton
- ▶ Principal Investigator for CaSDaR (Careers and Skills for Data-driven Research)
- ▶ Pathfinder Lead on Process Recording for PSDI
- ▶ Research Interests: Semantic Web Technologies, IoT, Research Data Management, Digitisation, Lab of the Future, Paperless Labs, Re-use of Technology
- ▶ @SamiKanza

The current situation

- ▶ Research data is growing at an exponential rates, this could provide great opportunities...but...
- ▶ Much of this data is stored in random places and cannot be located.
- ▶ Even when data can be located, it is frequently unintelligible
- ▶ Research and data generation is being wasted due to these issues as people cannot build on others work

Cartoon created by ErrantScience.com for AI4SD: licensed under [CC-BY-NC](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/)

www.nature.com/scientificdata

SCIENTIFIC DATA

Amended: Addendum

OPEN **Comment: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship**

SUBJECT CATEGORIES

- » Research data
- » Publication characteristics

Mark D. Wilkinson *et al.*[#]

There is an urgent need to improve the infrastructure supporting the reuse of scholarly data. A diverse set of stakeholders—representing academia, industry, funding agencies, and scholarly publishers—have come together to design and jointly endorse a concise and measurable set of principles that we refer to as the FAIR Data Principles. The intent is that these may act as a guideline for those wishing to enhance the reusability of their data holdings. Distinct from peer initiatives that focus on the human scholar, the FAIR Principles put specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data, in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals. This Comment is the first formal publication of the FAIR Principles, and includes the rationale behind them, and some exemplar implementations in the community.

Received: 10 December 2015
Accepted: 12 February 2016
Published: 15 March 2016

▶ A set of principles to ensure that data is:

- ▶ F – Findable
- ▶ A – Accessible
- ▶ I – Interoperable
- ▶ R – Reusable

¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Take that, and rewind it back

Photograph of Sharkcat transformed by Victoria Hooper using ChatGPT

Sharkcat's
got the
beat to
make your
data go...

FAIRs focus is very end-based

- ▶ FAIR is a great set of principles for data sharing
- ▶ However, this results in the principles primarily describing how to SHARE data in a re-usable fashion
- ▶ We need to dial it back and consider how to CREATE data that can then be CURATED and SHARED for re-use

"ALL RESEARCH SHOULD AIM TO BE F.A.I.R."

#FIGSHAREFEST

	GOOD	BAD
F INDABLE	ONLINE DATABASE	FILING CABINET IN A BATH IN THE BASEMENT UNDER A LEAKING PIPE
A CCESSABLE	OPEN ACCESS FOR EVERYONE (NO LOGIN)	THE FILING CABINET ALSO IS HOME TO A NEST OF WILD BADGERS
I NTEROPERABLE	ALL DATA IS IN OPEN FORMATS	ALL DOCUMENTS ARE PRINTED IN COMIC SANS AND WRITTEN IN ESPERANTO
R EUSEABLE	GOOD META DATA AND SECURELY STORED FOR 10 YEARS	THE PAPER EXPLODES IF IT'S READ

ERRANTSCIENCE.COM

R is for Re-useable

- ▶ R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
- ▶ R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
- ▶ R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
- ▶ R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

But this doesn't really tell me how to make my data re-useable in the fuller sense!!!

R is for Re-useable

- ▶ Not just about Data, need to consider Tools, Code, Methods, Context
- ▶ How could/would your work be re-used, replicated, reproduced or repurposed
 - ▶ Re-use – re-use the data (or run the software) in the same manner
 - ▶ Replicate – repeat entire research from scratch including data collection and analysis
 - ▶ Reproduce – reanalyse the existing data in the same manner
 - ▶ Repurpose – use existing data or software for a new purpose
- ▶ Use READMEs to explain HOW to make use of the data, and Metadata to define data attributes, terms of use and provenance

No that still
doesn't help
me!
DO BETTER!

Re-use starts with Creation

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- ▶ The reusable principles provide a mechanism for others to understand what your data is and how to use it
- ▶ However, they do not cover how to **CREATE** data that is actually usable in the first place

Data Creation

<https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/research-data-management-toolkit>

- ▶ Many of the issues with data re-use start at the creation/collection stage
- ▶ Data creation requires
 - ▶ Proper planning (DMPs)
 - ▶ How are you going to collect your data?
 - ▶ How are you going to standardise data entry?
 - ▶ How are you going to mitigate against missing or incomplete data records?
 - ▶ What are the ethical considerations?

Data Curation

- ▶ Data curation is much easier with robust well collected/created data
- ▶ However, it still retains a high level of complexity to:
 - ▶ Ensuring data is accurate of of high quality
 - ▶ Ensure that data is standardised and made available in interoperable formats
 - ▶ Create standardised interoperable metadata to enable discoverability and re-usability
 - ▶ Manage the storage and security of the data

BEFORE WE HAVE ALL THE DATA POINTS,
IT COULD BE ANYTHING...

Data Sharing

DATA PUBLISHING	
GOOD	BAD
DATA REPOSITORY	STICKY NOTE ON YOUR DOOR
INSTITUTIONAL ARCHIVE	SUPPLEMENTARY DATA
	BOTTOM OF A WELL

ERRANTSCIENCE.COM

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- ▶ Highly curated robust datasets are well placed for sharing
- ▶ This requires:
 - ▶ Acquiring DOIs
 - ▶ Identifying relevant repositories for data to be deposited and indexed
 - ▶ Setting relevant access levels and licensing for re-use
 - ▶ Making data available in interoperable formats
 - ▶ Providing metadata and READMEs alongside the data

FAIR Requirements

► Implementing FAIR fully to consider creation and curation requires knowledge of:

- Data Management Planning
- Data Collection & Curation
- Metadata Generation and appropriate schemas for generic/domain specific metadata
- Ethics & Data Governance
- Publication & Data Sharing
- Repositories

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Should we really expect researchers to know all of this on an expert level?

HELL NO!!!
(Did you miss me?)

So, what is the solution?

- ▶ This is not something that can be purely solved on a technical level
- ▶ We need human intervention to help improve our data
- ▶ However, finding the full range of skills in one person to implement FAIR is hard enough, so we cannot expect researchers to possess all of these skills and knowledge!
- ▶ **We need people with the technical skills and domain knowledge to work together with researchers to create FAIR datasets**
- ▶ **We need Data Stewards**

If anyone says
“throw it at an AI”
I’ll be very
displeased...!

Why we need Data Stewards

- ▶ We need Data Stewards
 - To create data that is **worth sharing**
 - To ensure that **FAIR** principles can be implemented
 - To get the best value out of our data and scientific research
 - To avoid repetition of work because data cannot be re-used

The role of Data Stewards

The need for Data Stewards across the research data lifecycle

Lets just do that then?

This sounds good
but...how well
established are Data
Stewards? Is this a
feasible suggestion?

Establishing Data Stewards

- ▶ Data Stewards are slowly starting to become established as a key role in FAIR data production
- ▶ They are starting to fall under the bracket of "Research Technical Professionals" much like Software Engineers and Data Scientists
- ▶ Many people are already doing roles that fall under the remit of data stewardship even if it is not badged under that name e.g. librarians, research data managers, data curators, etc.
- ▶ **Despite this progress, we are woefully short of skilled data stewards, and the support for data stewards, and this needs to change**

If only someone
was trying to help
with that...

Enter CaSDaR Stage Left

UK Research
and Innovation

Funded by the UKRI
RTP Call

CaSDaR
Careers and Skills for
Data-driven Research

A Network+ for
Data Stewards

1st April 2025 –
31st March 2029

University of
Southampton

Led out of the
University of
Southampton

Sounds great...
**HEY WHY AM I
PURPLE?!?!?!?**

CaSDaR Team

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CaSDaR Roadmap & Aims

Empowering Data Stewards for Research Excellence

Build a Community

Create a supportive, diverse, inclusive, self sustaining community for data stewards. Run flagship events to bring the community together and allow them to drive us.

Establish Data Stewards

“Learn by doing”. Fund data stewards as “researchers on the ground” to understand roles and challenges across different institutions and (under represented) disciplines.

Develop Career Pathways

Establish clear and accessible career pathways, with entry level routes, progression opportunities, taking into account the different skill requirements.

Recognition & Cultural Change

Promote the recognition of data stewards, highlighting their critical role in managing and preserving research data. Establish a culture that values and supports data stewards.

Enabling Sustainability

Develop sustainable models for data stewardship. Establish Data Stewardship Association that will empower our community to be self managed both during and after the grant.

CaSDaR Deliverables

Institutional Framework

Models for roles, responsibilities, competencies, and career progression.

Resource Repository

Online database of job descriptions, career resources, and best practices.

Skills Assessment

Report on UK data stewardship skills gaps to inform and enable tailored training.

CaSDaR Analysis Report

Impact analysis of CaSDaR activities on data stewardship and the community.

Grant Awards

Support Data Steward positions across different domains & UK research institutions.

Data Stewardship Association

Formal association with mission, governance, and membership criteria.

CaSDaR Events

CaSDaR Funding Calls

Data Steward Fellowship

Support Data Steward positions across different domains & UK research institutions

Open Funding Calls

Proposals for data stewardship projects

Data Steward Internships

Internship opportunities linked with projects that require different types of data stewardship

These will be reviewed by an expert panel with interdisciplinary experiences in data stewardship. **Join us at our launch on the 18th September to find out more!**

CaSDaR's Core Values & Commitments

Inclusivity

- Embed EDI principles across all activities
- Provide inclusive, flexible support for all activities
- Accessible Venues for Meetings & Hybrid Events
- Bursary fund for event attendance

Collaboration

- Foster a sense of belonging for all data stewards
- Promote teamwork and knowledge sharing within the data stewardship community

Integrity

- Promote and upskill researchers in responsible and ethical data stewardship practices

Recognition

- Recognise and credit all contributions to research data
- Targeted support for early career researchers for progression and acknowledgement

Sustainability

- Ensure long-term sustainability of data stewardship
- Support long-term preservation and accessibility of research data

National & International Data Steward Networks & Supporting Initiatives

- [Sonrai \(The Irish Data Stewardship Network\)](#)

- Website: <https://datastewards.ie/>
- Aims to promote and support the development of data stewardship skills across Ireland's research landscape, ensuring the curdion, preservation, and dissemination of national data assets in alignment with FAIR principles

- [Data Steward Interest Group \(The Netherlands\)](#)

- Website: <https://tdccnl/dsig/>
- This group is aiming to establish a community hub for data stewardship that enables informal and inclusive knowledge and experience exchange.

- [NFDI \(The German National Data Infrastructure\)](#)

- Website: <https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>
- The NFDI plays a crucial role in data stewardship by developing and implementing standards, tools, and best practices for managing research data. Many groups within the NFDI support data stewardship including NFDI4Chem https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base/docs/data_steward/ and NFDI4Bioimage <https://nfdi4bioimage.de/about-us/data-stewardship-team/>

- [World Data System](#)

- Website: <https://worlddatasystem.org/>
- The World Data System (WDS) enhances data stewardship by promoting the long-term stewardship and accessibility of quality-assured scientific data and run the prestigious Data Stewardship Awards.

- [Research Data Alliance – Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group](#)

- Website: <https://www.rda-alliance.org/groups/professionalising-data-stewardship-ig/members/all-members/>
- This is an RDA interest group on professionalising data stewardship

- [Digital Data Curation \(DCC\)](#)

- Website: <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/>
- DCC is dedicated to improving data stewardship in the research community and runs regular events to support this

- [Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure](#)

- Website: www.psdia.ac.uk
- PSDI is working hard to establish a community of data stewards across the physical sciences

- [STEP-UP](#)

- Website: <https://step-up.ac.uk/>
- Imperial College London / University College London / Kings College London / University of Westminster– This project is developing communities, training and career opportunities to support "digital Research Technical Professionals" (DRTPs)

Save the Date for our Townhall Launch!

18th September 2025
Hybrid Townhall Launch
Birmingham Library & Online
Lunch & Refreshments Provided
Opportunities to present
Lightning Talks & Posters

- ▶ Hear inspirational stories from Data Stewards about their journeys
- ▶ Gain insights from our expert project partners about the vital role of Data Stewardship
- ▶ Hear about related Data Stewardship initiatives
- ▶ Network with likeminded people and meet useful contacts across the breadth of data stewardship
- ▶ Discuss key issues and areas of data stewardship including training, career progression and the role of data stewardship
- ▶ Find out all about our upcoming funding call!

Oh Boy! I'll definitely be there!

Getting involved with CaSDaR

 www.casdar.ac.uk (in dev)

 CaSDaRNetwork

 @ CaSDaRNetwork

 @casdarnetwork.bsky.social

 @casdarnetwork@mstdn.science

 @ CaSDaRNetwork

<https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/CASDAR>

Thanks for listening

WOOHOO I'M THE
RIGHT COLOUR
AGAIN!!

PSDI

**PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE**

Data Management Plans for the Physical Sciences

Exploring Data Curation in the Physical Sciences: PSDI Roadshow
8th July 2025

Dr Cerys Willoughby & Dr Louise Saul
University of Southampton

<https://www.psd.ac.uk/>

Benefits of Data Management Plans

- ▶ Improving data management
- ▶ Ensuring proper storage and protection of the data
- ▶ Considering long-term preservation and curation
- ▶ Making it easier to share the data
- ▶ Enhancing reproducibility by documenting the processes and provenance of the data
- ▶ Compliance with funder and institutional requirements
- ▶ Supporting ethical and legal considerations
- ▶ Metadata could be reused

Barriers for Data Management Plans

- ▶ Time and effort
- ▶ Reliance on filling in lots of boxes with text
- ▶ Lack of subject-specific examples for physical sciences
- ▶ Guidance is generic or lacks relevancy to physical sciences data
- ▶ Seen as a box-ticking exercise
- ▶ Not perceived as a useful living document

A Data Management Plan for Physical Sciences

- ▶ Examples of good practice shared by the community? ✘
- ▶ Examples of good practice from School of Chemistry at Southampton? ✘
- ▶ Problems: Not much out there, very specific and difficult to anonymise, few examples of 'good practice'
- ▶ NFDI4Chem work: results from RDA WG Discipline-specific Guidance for DMP online survey, NFDI4Chem Survey & Interviews; developed a DMP
- ▶ Updated for a UK audience
- ▶ Followed DCC Guidance on what should be in a DMP

A Data Management Plan for PSDI

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `guidance.psd.ac.uk/docu.../guidance/data-management/data-management-planning/dmps/psdi-dmp`. The page is titled "Data Management Plan for the Physical Sciences" and is part of the "PSDI Knowledge Base". The left sidebar contains a navigation menu with categories like "Getting started with PSDI", "Guidance", "Research Data Management", "Data Management Planning", "Data Management Plans", "Completed DMP Example", "Contributor Record", "Collaborative Research", "Getting Help with RDM", "Sharing Data and FAIR", "Digital Notebooks and ELNs", "Metadata", "PSDI Resources", "Case Studies", "IT Support", and "Training". The main content area features a breadcrumb trail: "Guidance > Research Data Management > Data Management Plannings > Data Management Plans > DMP for Physical Sciences". The main heading is "Data Management Plan for the Physical Sciences". Below it, a paragraph explains that this is a DMP tailored for the Physical Sciences, designed to help researchers think about data production, safety, and future usability. An "INFO" box highlights that the DMP is a work in progress, based on a chemistry-specific template from NFDI4Chem and Zenodo, and follows the Digital Curation Centre (DCC) guidelines. A link is provided for a "Data Management Plan Example for Physical Sciences". The "About this Data Management Plan" section includes several questions: "What is the ID of this data management plan?", "Who owns this data management plan?", "What updates have been made to this data management plan?", and "Who has reviewed this data management plan?". The "About the Research" section includes questions about the research project, regulations, and data collection. The "About the Data" section includes questions about data creation, reuse, organization, and formats. The "Data Documentation" section includes questions about documentation and a question about maintaining links between data and notebooks. The "Data Quality" section includes a question about quality controls. The "Data Storage and Security" section includes questions about storage requirements, data sharing, and backup plans. A cat in a tuxedo is visible in the bottom right corner of the browser window.

We need feedback from the community!

**We know
it's not
purrfect!**

- ▶ It's very long!
- ▶ It needs to be in an alternative format:
 - ▶ form
 - ▶ Word
 - ▶ Excel
 - ▶ ??
- ▶ Option to hide guidance?
- ▶ More completed examples from different disciplines

A few questions from you

We'll give you 10 minutes to look at <https://tinyurl.com/psdi-dmp> the DMP and then ask you the following questions:

- ▶ Is there a need for a physical sciences DMP?
- ▶ Would it be helpful for us to provide the DMP in a form format, with dropdowns and radio buttons for example?
- ▶ Which sections are the most important?
- ▶ What have we missed from this DMP – is there anything that would improve it?
- ▶ Do you have an idea for a better tool to capture this information?

Please note down any thoughts as you go through, and we are grateful for more in-depth feedback after the session if anyone would like to provide it

VEVOX SESSION

- ▶ Go to vevox.com
- ▶ Enter the session ID: 142-560-419

Is there a need for a physical sciences DMP?

Would it be helpful for us to provide the DMP in a form format, with dropdowns and radio buttons for example?

2. Would it be helpful for us to provide the DMP in a form format, with dropdowns and radio buttons for example?

15

15 responses

yes

no

Which sections are the most important?

What have we missed from this DMP – is there anything that would improve it?

something like 'Research council specific guidelines must be obeyed' ? Is it physically possible t...

Notion of granularity of data - even within technique types there are variations in what one could/should do

Licensing details - open government licence etc Do physical science projects always have...

No

Requires a lot of pre-knowledge!

Thinking about taxonomies and how the DMP could be used in the process of creating the data...

More cross links to guidance? Maybe per section

Ironically, missing data. There should be a strategy for handling missing data and coding in reasons. E....

Requirements for dataset DOI's on data produced during the project - how many, etc.

Signposting (even if just "ask your boss!")

Do you have an idea for a better tool to capture this information?

No!

Word doc with detailed revision/version notes detailing edits throughout project...

Either a word document, or if it is a form, something that you can come back to and edit over time an...

Data stewardship wizard (ds-wizard.org)

Have a triage start, so the actual DMP is output of inputs made. IOW, user doesn't edit the actual document...

A web interface with branching e.g. If you tick ethical considerations it opens up the relevan...

Fair wizard is used by BODC and the EDS and is tailored to environmental data

ERNs

No!

GITHUB!

**Thank you for
contributing!**

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Plugging Physical Sciences research data into PSDI via metadata and standards – why and how?

Dr Aileen Day (PSDI metadata lead)

Exploring Data Curation and Management in Physical Sciences: PSDI
Roadshow @ Southampton

8th July 2025

Plugging Physical Sciences research data into PSDI via metadata and standards – why and how?

Outline:

- ▶ PSDI metadata overview
- ▶ Plugging into PSDI via these metadata profiles:
 - ▶ why and how?

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

PSDI metadata

the glue that brings PSDI together

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

What We Provide

<https://resources.psd.ac.uk/>

What We Provide

Search

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

<https://data-search.psd.ac.uk/>

Find a
Substance

Find a
Publication
Reference

Find Chemical
Product Availability

Advanced
Search

Cross Data Search

Resource Themes

Resource Themes are collections of related resources aligned to specific physical sciences research areas.

Data Sources

Data sources include databases, repositories, datasets, and collections.

Services

Services are online software for accessing or processing data.

Tools

Tools are downloadable applications that let you integrate data and functionality into your own workflows.

Guidance

Guidance resources are educational and support materials that help you to work with data and the resources that PSDI provides.

PSDI Metadata

▶ Top-level PSDI metadata

PSDI metadata
Overview of PSDI metadata

Summary

The PSDI metadata for the **Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)** project.

Guidance about the PSDI metadata can be found at **PSDI metadata guidance in the PSDI knowledgebase.**

The metadata is made available in **JSON-LD format** (.jsonld files) and equivalent **Terse RDF Triple Language** (.ttl files).

Metadata available:

- <https://psdi-uk.github.io/metadata/>
- [psdi-voc.jsonld/psdi-voc.ttl](#) - SKOS vocabulary defining nomenclature used within the PSDI project and the resulting PSDI infrastructure and its platform
- [psdi-dcat.jsonld/psdi-dcat.ttl](#) - DCAT description of catalogue of resources (data, services, tools and guidance) made available via PSDI
- [psdi-dcat-ext.jsonld/psdi-dcat-ext.ttl](#) - extension of DCAT to describe PSDI catalogue
- [psdi-dcat-shacl.jsonld/psdi-dcat-shacl.ttl](#) - shacl shape for validation of psdi-dcat PSDI catalogue

▶ Documentation

PSDI Knowledge Base
Getting Started | Guidance | IT Support | Training

PSDI Metadata

Guidance for physical science data users and contributors about PSDI metadata.

- Terminology**
Definitions of top-level nomenclature us...
- Overview**
Overview of guidance about metadata
- General Guidelines**
Description of general guidelines which ...
- Vocabulary Description**
Description of PSDI Vocabulary
- Resource Catalogue Des...**
Description of PSDI Resource Catalogue
- Checking Guidelines**
Description of Guidelines for checking P...

Previous: [Metadata in the Physical Sciences](#) | Next: [Terminology](#)

Funding
PSDI acknowledges the funding support by the EPSRC grants EP/X032701/1, EP/X032663/1 and EP/W032252/1

Useful Links
[PSDI Home](#)
[Contact Us](#)
[Privacy](#)
[Terms and Conditions](#)

Connect
[Mailing List](#)
[in](#) [X](#) [YouTube](#) [Twitter](#)
[m](#)

PSDI Metadata – top-down approach

- ▶ Metadata that supports PSDI Resource Catalogue
- ▶ Metadata that supports PSDI Cross Data Search

PSDI Metadata

– using existing standards

Wherever possible we use existing standards, ontologies, vocabularies, community best practices

- ▶ e.g. Following CDIF^{1,2} recommendations

CDIF is “*first and foremost a practical exercise: how can we find a set of common standards and technology approaches that will enable us to implement FAIR for cross-domain scenarios using things which exist today*”

Introducing CDIF — Cross Domain | X

cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/introduction.html

What is CDIF

CDIF is not intended to replace existing community standards, but to supplement them for communication across domain and infrastructure boundaries. It does not aim to replace the specific models needed within different domains, but it does aim to establish a foundation of common metadata which can support a core set of FAIR functionality. Real-world examples of large-scale standards-based exchange networks, such as the [Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange](#) (SDMX) and the [Ocean InfoHub](#) (ODIS) have been used as inspiration for the overall approach, to ensure its feasibility for practical implementation. This draft includes links to early prototypes for such data as the Sustainable Development Goal Indicators and some of their source data, showing how the mining of the native standard descriptions of the source, to produce its equivalent in CDIF, can support disaggregation and integration of that data with other sources.

There is a wealth of research on how FAIR can be implemented, and investigations into this subject show no sign of abating. CDIF is not a research project, nor does it intend to outline the best possible solution to the challenges of FAIR implementation. Instead, it is first and

1. [D2 .3 Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework CDIF Report \(Synthesising Recommendations for Disciplines and Cross-Disciplinary Research Area report\)](#) is a recent [WorldFAIR](#) output
2. <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/introduction.html>

PSDI Metadata

– using existing standards

Wherever possible we use existing standards, ontologies, vocabularies, community best practices

- ▶ e.g. Following CDIF^{1,2} recommendations

CDIF is “*first and foremost a practical exercise: how can we find a set of common standards and technology approaches that will enable us to implement FAIR for cross-domain scenarios using things which exist today*”

1. [D2 .3 Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework CDIF Report \(Synthesising Recommendations for Disciplines and Cross-Disciplinary Research Area report\)](#) is a recent [WorldFAIR](#) output
2. <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/introduction.html>

PSDI Metadata

– using existing standards

SKOS vocabulary (<https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-primer/>)

DCAT resource catalogue (<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>)

OPTIMADE (<https://www.optimade.org/>)

ORCID (<https://orcid.org/>)

ROR (<https://ror.org/>)

Plugging Physical Sciences research data into PSDI via metadata and standards – why and how?

Outline:

- ▶ PSDI metadata overview
- ▶ Plugging into PSDI via these metadata profiles:
 - ▶ why and how?

PSDI Metadata SKOS vocabulary

PSDI Terminology (<https://guidance.psd.ac.uk/docusaurus-pages/docs/guidance/metadata/psdi-metadata/psdi-terminology>)

```

< > ↻ metadata.psd.ac.uk/psdi-voc.jsonld ☆ 🗄️ 🗉 ⋮
Pretty print
{
  "skos:inScheme": "psdiVoc:vocabularyConceptScheme",
  "skos:example": [
    "user registration",
    "access management",
    "structure searching",
    "format conversion service"
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  "skos:example": [
    "format conversion tool",
    "MagresView library"
  ]
}

```

<https://metadata.psd.ac.uk/psdi-skos.jsonld>, SKOS format
(<https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-primer/>)

Plugging into PSDI step 1: high level resource description

Plugging Physical Sciences research data into PSDI via metadata and standards – why and how?

Outline:

- ▶ PSDI metadata overview
- ▶ Plugging into PSDI via these metadata profiles:
 - ▶ why and how?

PSDI Metadata DCAT Resource Catalogue

What we Provide - PSDI (<https://resources.psd.ac.uk/>)

PSDI Metadata DCAT Resource Catalogue

Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) Magres Database
Sathya Sai Seetharamani & John Kane Swinton

What We Provide » Data Sources » Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) Magres Database

The Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) database of calculated solid-state NMR data from DFT codes in MAGRES format.

Quick Links
Visit →
Resource Theme →

To use this resource go to the **resource landing page**.

This resource is part of the **Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) resource theme**.

Linked Resources
Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) MAGRES Database Search

Further Information
CCP-NC database - Frequently Asked Questions

Publisher
PSDI

Access
Open Access

Licenses
PDOL-1.0
ODC-By-1.0
CC-BY-4.0

Contact
<http://www.ccpnc.ac.uk/contact>

Citation
Please cite: "Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) MAGRES Database". <https://www.ccpnc.ac.uk/database/>, PSDI, accessed on CURRENT_DATE. Please also follow the citation guidelines associated with the assigned licensing of each record, including its MRD number, the creator(s) of the record and any associated publication.

Keywords and Subjects
SSNMR NMR EFG Magnetic Shielding Magres DFT CASTEP Quantum Espresso

Resources, descriptions and details are retrieved from DCAT jsonld metadata

← → ↻ 🌐 metadata.psd.ac.uk/psdi-dcat.jsonld 🔍 ☆ 📄 📧 ⋮

pretty print

```

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}
},
{
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  "@type": "skos:Concept",
  "@id": "http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Collection"
},
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  "DFT",
  "Magres",
  "SSNMR",
  "Crystallography"
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  }
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"dcterms:publisher": {
  "foaf:name": "PSDI",
  "@type": "foaf:Agent",
  "@id": "http://www.psd.ac.uk"
}

```

<https://metadata.psd.ac.uk/psdi-dcat.jsonld>
DCAT format (<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>)

Plugging into PSDI step 2: resource description for catalogue

Python
scripts feed
these into
psdi-
dcat.jsonld

psdiCatalogueAddition_PF6.xlsx

File Home Insert Page Layout Formulas Data Review View Automate Help Acrobat

C9 : X ✓ fx ✓ CCP-NC Magres database

	A	B	C
7	@type		dcat:Dataset
8	dcterms:title		Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) Magres Database
9	rdfs:label		CCP-NC Magres database
10	dcterms:type		Dataset (http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Dataset)
11	dcterms:description		The Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) database of calculated solid-state NMR data from DFT codes in MAGRES format.
12	dcat:keyword		SSNMR; NMR; EFG; Magnetic Shielding; Magres; DFT; CASTEP; Quantum Espresso
13	dcat:theme		quantum chemistry (http://data.europa.eu/8mn/euroscivoc/7aca9814-d7a5-43b2-8521-0fa53e8bd36a); condensed matter physics (http://data.europa.eu/8mn/euroscivoc/c61cf6c6-8b52-4fbb-9b30-b09659e476cf)
14	dcterms:publisher		PSDI (http://www.psd.ac.uk)
15	dcterms:creator		Sathya Sai Seetharaman (https://orcid.org/0009-0006-9138-9585); John Kane Shenton (https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4485-3446)
16	prov:qualifiedAttribution		
17	prov:qualifiedAttribution dcat:hadRole		
18	dcat:landingPage		CCP-NC Database (http://www.ccpnc.ac.uk/database/)
19	dcat:contactPoint		http://www.ccpnc.ac.uk/contact
20	dcterms:conformsTo		magres (http://www.ccpnc.ac.uk/docs/magres/magres-format.pdf)
21	dcterms:language		en (http://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/iso639-1/en)
22	adms:status		http://purl.org/adms/status/UnderDevelopment
23	dcterms:issued		2018-03-19T10:46:52Z

DCAT_resourceTheme DCAT_service DCAT_data DCAT_tool DCAT_guidance

← → ↻ metadata.psd.ac.uk/psdi-dcat.jsonld

```

pretty print
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},
{
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  "@type": "dcat:Catalog",
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  "rdfs:label": "CCP-NC",
  "dcterms:type": {
    "skos:prefLabel": "Collection",
    "@type": "skos:Concept",
    "@id": "http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Collection"
  },
  "dcterms:description": "The Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) supports a multidisciplinary community by developing and integrating software tools that advance NMR crystallography. By combining experimental NMR with computational methods, CCP-NC enables researchers to gain atomic-scale insights into structure, disorder, and dynamics in the solid state. A key resource is its repository for first-principles NMR calculations, which standardises data using the .magres file format. The project also provides specialised software, such as MagresView, for data processing and visualisation, along with tools for electronic structure calculations and ab initio NMR parameter prediction. Additionally, CCP-NC offers training opportunities and access to high-performance computing (HPC) through the oung supercomputer, further enhancing research capabilities. Through these resources, CCP-NC empowers researchers to conduct cutting-edge NMR rystallography, improving efficiency, fostering collaboration, and expanding professional networks. By facilitating the development and adoption of advanced computational methods, the project contributes to the broader scientific community, driving innovation in materials research.",
  "dcat:keyword": [
    "NMR",
    "DFT",
    "Magres",
    "SSNMR",
    "Crystallography"
  ],
  "dcat:theme": [
    {
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      "@type": "skos:Concept",
      "@id": "http://data.europa.eu/8mn/euroscivoc/7aca9814-d7a5-43b2-8521-0fa53e8bd36a"
    },
    {
      "skos:prefLabel": "condensed matter physics",
      "@type": "skos:Concept",
      "@id": "http://data.europa.eu/8mn/euroscivoc/c61cf6c6-8b52-4fbb-9b30-b09659e476cf"
    }
  ],
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    "@type": "foaf:Agent",
    "@id": "http://www.psd.ac.uk"
  }
}

```

Currently gather resource theme and resource descriptions in Excel templates, collaboratively with resource owners

Plugging Physical Sciences research data into PSDI via metadata and standards – why and how?

Outline:

- ▶ PSDI metadata overview
- ▶ Plugging into PSDI via these metadata profiles:
 - ▶ why and how?

PSDI Cross Data Search

The screenshot shows the PSDI Cross Data Search web application. The browser address bar displays `data-search.psd.ac.uk/find-a-substance/all-substance`. The page header includes the PSDI logo and navigation links: **Find a Substance** (underlined), **Find a Publication Reference**, **Find Chemical Product Availability**, **Advanced Search**, **Login**, and a settings icon.

Cross Data Search

Navigation tabs: **All Substances** (selected), **Elemental Composition**, **Periodicity and Symmetry**, **Crystal Cell Parameters**

Chemical formula description

Here you can find a substance based on the chemical formula for a structure in a form chosen by data type. You can do either an exact match or retrieve all substances that contain the given keywords in their descriptions.

Descriptive chemical formula

Exact match

Select data sources to search **34**

Select data sources

Filter data sources by name or description, Esc to clear

● Only showing data sources supporting structures search type. **34** selected.

Hide descriptions

- Cambridge Structural Database**
A comprehensive curated collection of organic and metal-organic crystal structures determined using diffraction techniques, maintained by the CCDC.
[Visit resource catalogue](#)
- Crystallography Open Database**
Open-access collection of crystal structures of organic, inorganic, metal-organic compounds and minerals, excluding biopolymers.
[Visit resource catalogue](#)
- UK Catalysis Hub Datasets**
Data objects produced by UK Catalysis Hub researchers and listed on their web portal: <http://cdi.ukcatalysis.org/>
[Visit resource catalogue](#)
- UK Catalysis Hub Publications**
Publications produced by UK Catalysis Hub researchers and listed on their web portal: <http://cdi.ukcatalysis.org/>
[Visit resource catalogue](#)
- ChAS**

PSDI Cross Data Search uses OPTIMADE

We require the resource data to align with OPTIMADE core properties and PSDI namespace properties for maximum searchability...

optimade.org

OPTIMADE
Open Databases Integration
for Materials Design

About Resources Specification Contributors GitHub Forum Try It!

About us

The **Open Databases Integration for Materials Design** (OPTIMADE) consortium aims to make materials databases interoperable by developing a specification for a common REST API.

We have released version 1 of the OPTIMADE specification, with several databases already providing implementations. A full list is available on the [OPTIMADE providers dashboard](#).

25	29	59,521,800
PROVIDERS	DATABASES	STRUCTURES

PSDI Cross Data S

Align with OPTIMADE properties in:

- structures endpoint
(<https://schemas.optimade.org/defs/v1.2/entrytypes/optimade/structures>)
- references endpoint
(<https://schemas.optimade.org/defs/v1.2/entrytypes/optimade/references>)

data-search.psd.ac.uk/find-a-substance/all-substance

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Find a Substance Find a Publication Reference

All Substances Elemental Composition

Chemical formula description

Here you can find a substance based on the chemical formula. You can search for a specific formula to do either an exact match or retrieve all substances with similar formulas.

Descriptive chemical formula

e.g., (H₂O)₂ Na

Exact match

https://schemas.optimade.org/defs/v1.2/standards/optimade.html

OPTIMADE standard (standard)

This page documents an **OPTIMADE Standard Definition**. See <https://schemas.optimade.org/> for more information.

ID: <https://schemas.optimade.org/defs/v1.2/standards/optimade>
Definition name: optimade

Standard name: OPTIMADE standard
Description: The OPTIMADE standard node types and properties
Formats: [JSON] [MD]

This standard defines the following entrytypes:

- **structures** (entrytype) - <https://schemas.optimade.org/defs/v1.2/entrytypes/optimade/structures>
The structures entry type describes a crystal structure via its unit cell
- **files** (entrytype) - <https://schemas.optimade.org/defs/v1.2/entrytypes/optimade/files>
The files entry type describes a file with metadata and a URL to retrieve it
- **references** (entrytype) - <https://schemas.optimade.org/defs/v1.2/entrytypes/optimade/references>
The references entry type describes a reference

Requirements/Conventions:

- **Support:** MUST be implemented.
- **Support:** OPTIONAL.
- **Support:** OPTIONAL.

ed Publication Reference

 [PSDI knowledge base](#)

(H₂O)₂ Na". You may choose

PSDI – find a substance

What is a substance?

- ▶ everything made up of elements

data-search.psd.ac.uk/find-a-substance/all-substance

PSDI PHYSICAL SCIENCES DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Find a Substance Find a Publication Reference Find Chemical Product Availability Advanced Search Log

Cross Data Search

All Substances Elemental Composition Periodicity and Symmetry Crystal Cell Parameter Molecule Linked Publication Re

Chemical formula description

Here you can find a substance based on the chemical formula for a structure in a form chosen by data sources, for example "(H₂O)₂ Na". You can search to do either an exact match or retrieve all substances that contain the given keywords in their description.

Descriptive chemical formula

e.g., (H₂O)₂ Na

Exact match

Select data sources to search 34 Search

searching on OPTIMADE structure endpoint property:

- ▶ descriptive chemical formula (chemical_formula_descriptive)

This is the most widely-populated chemical formula property but others are available for searching in the "Advanced Search":

- ▶ reduced chemical formula (chemical_formula_reduced)
- ▶ Hill chemical formula (chemical_formula_hill)
- ▶ anonymous chemical formula (chemical_formula_anonymous)

PSDI – find a substance

OPTIMADE provides comprehensive definition of core properties e.g.

searching on OPTIMADE structure endpoint property:

descriptive chemical formula (chemical_formula_descriptive)

This is the most widely-populated chemical formula property but others are available for searching in the “Advanced Search”:

▶ reduced chemical formula (chemical_formula_reduced)

▶ Hill chemical formula (chemical_formula_hill)

▶ anonymous chemical formula (chemical_formula_anonymous)

elements:elements_ratios HAS ALL "A1":>0.3333, "A1":<0.3334 .

- descriptive chemical formula (chemical_formula_descriptive)** (property) - https://schemas.optimade.org/defs/v1.2/properties/optimade/structures/chemical_formula_descriptive
The chemical formula for a structure as a string in a form chosen by the API implementation.

Requirements/Conventions:

- Support:** SHOULD be supported by all implementations, i.e., SHOULD NOT be null .
- Query:** MUST be a queryable property with support for all mandatory filter features.
- Response:** MAY be included by default in the response.
- The chemical formula is given as a string consisting of properly capitalized element symbols followed by integers or decimal numbers, balanced parentheses, square, and curly brackets ((, \) , [, \] , {, \ } , commas, the +, -, : and = symbols. The parentheses are allowed to be followed by a number. Spaces are allowed anywhere except within chemical symbols. The order of elements and any groupings indicated by parentheses or brackets are chosen freely by the API implementation.
- The string SHOULD be arithmetically consistent with the element ratios in the `chemical_formula_reduced` property.
- It is RECOMMENDED, but not mandatory, that symbols, parentheses and brackets, if used, are used with the meanings prescribed by [IUPAC's Nomenclature of Organic Chemistry](#).

Query examples:

- Note: the free-form nature of this property is likely to make queries on it across different databases inconsistent.
- A filter that matches an exactly given formula: `chemical_formula_descriptive="(H2O)2 Na"` .
- A filter that does a partial match: `chemical_formula_descriptive CONTAINS "H2O"` .

- reduced chemical formula (chemical_formula_reduced)** (property) - https://schemas.optimade.org/defs/v1.2/properties/optimade/structures/chemical_formula_reduced
The reduced chemical formula for a structure as a string with element symbols and integer chemical proportion numbers

Select data sources to search 34

Search

PSDI – find a substance

What is a substance?

- ▶ everything made up of elements

data-search.psd.ac.uk/find-a-substance/periodic-table

All Substances **Elemental Composition** Periodicity and Symmetry Crystal Cell Parameter Molecule Linked Publication Reference

Number of elements
Here you can find a substance based on the number of different elements which it contains. You can either give an exact value or provide a range, e.g., minimum of 3 and a maximum of 5 elements. Open ranges can be specified by leaving the minimum or maximum values blank e.g., providing only a minimum value of 3 effectively means that substances containing at least 3 or more elements should be present in the results.

Number of elements
e.g., 3
1 2 3 4 5 Range

Elements and ratios
Here you can find a substance based on the elements which it contains. You may specify elements which *must* be included, *can* be included or elements which must be *excluded* from results. For each element which must or can be included in the results, you may additionally specify a *ratio*, using a value between 0 and 1 which indicates the relative proportion of the element in the substance.

Must include elements 0 Can include elements 0 Exclude elements 0

Auto expand dropdowns when selecting

Table size: [small](#), [large](#), [largest](#)

H																			He					
Li	Be																		B	C	N	O	F	Ne
Na	Mg																		Al	Si	P	S	Cl	Ar
K	Ca	Sc	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	As	Se	Br	Kr							
Rb	Sr	Y	Zr	Nb	Mo	Tc	Ru	Rh	Pd	Ag	Cd	In	Sn	Sb	Te	I	Xe							
Cs	Ba	57-71	Hf	Ta	W	Re	Os	Ir	Pt	Au	Hg	Tl	Pb	Bi	Po	At	Rn							
Fr	Ra	89-103	Rf	Db	Sg	Bh	Hs	Mt	Ds	Rg	Cn	Nh	Fl	Mc	Lv	Ts	Og							
			La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Pm	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu							
			Ac	Th	Pa	U	Np	Pu	Am	Cm	Bk	Cf	Es	Fm	Md	No	Lr							

Select data sources to search 34 Search

searching on OPTIMADE
structure endpoint property:

number of elements
(nelements)

elements

elements ratios
(elements_ratios)

PSDI – find a substance

If it has periodicity and symmetry:

- ▶ 3-Dimensional (crystal), 2-Dimensional (surface), 1-Dimensional (wire)...
- ▶ molecules are zero-dimensional crystal structure in OPTIMADE

data-search.psd.ac.uk/find-a-substance/periodicity-and-symmetry

PSDI PHYSICAL SCIENCES DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Find a Substance Find a Publication Reference Find Chemical Product Availability Advanced Search Login

Cross Data Search

All Substances Elemental Composition **Periodicity and Symmetry** Crystal Cell Parameter Molecule Linked Publication Reference

PSDI knowledge base

Periodicity
Here you can find a substance based on its periodicity (the number of periodic dimensions in the structure). You can select multiple periodicity values. Note that some symmetry options below are only applicable for periodicity of 3 so may become unavailable for periodicities less than this.

0 (e.g., a single molecule) 1 (e.g., a carbon nanotube) 2 (e.g., a 2D surface/slab) 3 (e.g., a bulk crystal structure)

Symmetry
Here you can find a substance based on its symmetry properties. Searching by Hall symbols or space group number are only available if you selected a periodicity of 3 above (they are only applicable for crystal structures). The Hall space group symbol specifies the symmetry of the structure as defined in Hall, S. R. (1981), Acta Cryst. A37, 517-525 and erratum (1981), A37, 921, for example "P 2c -2ac". The space group number for the structure specifies the space group assigned by the International Tables for Crystallography Vol. A, for example "42".

You can also search for the number of sites in the structure. You can either give an exact value or provide a range, e.g., minimum of 3 and a maximum of 5 sites. Open ranges can be specified by leaving the minimum or maximum values blank, e.g., providing a minimum value of 3 means that only substances containing 3 or more sites will be present in the results.

Hall symbols separated by space: e.g., P 2c -2ac

Space group number: Enter an integer between 1 and 230

Number of sites: e.g., 42

1 2 3 4 5 Range

Select data sources to search 34 Search

searching on OPTIMADE
structure endpoint properties:

dimension types
(dimension_types)

Hall space group symbol
(space_group_symbol_hall)

space group IT number
(space_group_it_number)

number of sites (property)

PSDI – find a substance

► If it is a crystal structure

data-search.psd.ac.uk/find-a-substance/crystal-cell-parameter

PSDI PHYSICAL SCIENCES DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Find a Substance Find a Publication Reference Find Chemical Product Availability Advanced Search Login

Cross Data Search

All Substances Elemental Composition Periodicity and Symmetry **Crystal Cell Parameter** Molecule Linked Publication Reference

PSDI knowledge base

Using any of the fields in this screen will automatically restrict target data sources. This happens when certain data types are present only on certain data sources. Using this screen will restrict data sources to the following: Crystallography Open Database, Theoretical Crystallography Open Database.

Crystal cell parameters

Here you can find a substance based on lattice parameters for *unit cell lengths* a , b & c and for *unit cell angles* α , β & γ of crystal structures. Cell lengths are given in Angstroms (Å) and cell angles in degrees. Additionally, you may change our default tolerances for angles and lengths. We generate minimum and maximum bounds using these tolerances and retrieve all substances in the resulting ranges.

Unit cell lengths

a	b	c	Tolerance
e.g., 0.3524	e.g., 0.3524	e.g., 0.3524	0.01

Unit cell angles

α	β	γ	Tolerance
e.g., 90	e.g., 90	e.g., 90	0.01

Select data sources to search 34 Search

► searching on custom properties for cell parameters: a , b , c , α , β , γ

► soon to be defined in PSDI namespace

► (note that OPTIMADE captures the alternative lattice vectors (lattice_vectors) which we do not use but can be searched on in Advanced Search)

PSDI – find a substance

► If it is a molecule

data-search.psd.ac.uk/find-a-substance/molecule

PSDI PHYSICAL SCIENCES DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Find a Substance Find a Publication Reference Find Chemical Product Availability Advanced Search Login

Cross Data Search

All Substances Elemental Composition Periodicity and Symmetry Crystal Cell Parameter **Molecule** Linked Publication Reference

PSDI knowledge base

Warning: Using any of the fields in this screen will automatically restrict target data sources. This happens when certain data types are present only on certain data sources. Using this screen will restrict data sources to the following: ChASe, Propersea, Chemotion, Cambridge Structural Database, Crystallography Open Database, Theoretical Crystallography Open Database.

Chemical identifiers

Here you can find a substance using a chemical identifier, either a *SMILES* or an *InChI* string. If you already have an identifier, you can simply paste it below and select the correct identifier type.

Another alternative is to draw a molecule yourself using ChemDoodle™ - click the button below to load the ChemDoodle™ web application. You can also import a molecule into ChemDoodle™ using your own data in any of the supported formats, e.g., SMILES or InChI.

Identifier

Chemical identifier as InChI or SMILES

SMILES InChI

Draw Molecule

Select data sources to search 34 Search

- searching on custom properties (InChI and SMILES) molecular descriptors
- simple text search currently
- There is work on a OPTIMADE cheminformatics namespace for to standardise these

PSDI – find a substance

2D ChemDoodle 3D ChemDoodle Import

Use this tab to draw a molecule with ChemDoodle™ web application. A string representation (chemical identifier) will be automatically generated below as you make modifications, either as SMILES or InChI depending on your selection. Once the drawing is complete, use "Done" button to copy the identifier to the input area before you run a search. You can also use "Import" tab to load a molecule into ChemDoodle™ if you want to use your own data in any of the supported formats.

Click on "Close ChemDoodle" to go back.

CH₃

Molecule-drawer available in PSDI search

ChemDoodle®

Close ChemDoodle

Done

SMILES InChI

Your drawing represented as SMILES identifier:

c1(ccccc1)C

Done

Draw Molecule

Select data sources to search 34 Search

- ▶ searching on custom properties (InChI and SMILES) molecular descriptors
- ▶ simple text search currently
- ▶ There is work on a OPTIMADE cheminformatics namespace for to standardise these

Plugging into PSDI step 3: PSDI Cross Data Search variables

- ▶ Align substance definition and properties to OPTIMADE structures endpoint where applicable, particularly those which have been highlighted above in PSDI Cross Data Search
- ▶ Align linked publication details to OPTIMADE references endpoint
- ▶ Resources feed into PSDI Cross Data Search either by:
 1. Becoming an OPTIMADE database provider and realising an OPTIMADE API to serve data from one or more databases
 2. Indexing data via backend PSDI indexing service (via an alternative API)

Plugging Physical Sciences research data into PSDI via metadata and standards – why and how?

Outline:

- ▶ PSDI metadata overview
- ▶ Plugging into PSDI via these metadata profiles:
 - ▶ why and how?

Thankyou for listening!

Any questions?

PSDI terminology

PSDI Resource Catalogue

PSDI Cross Data Search

SKOS vocabulary

DCAT resource catalogue

OPTIMADE

Generation and curation of large quantities of predicted crystal structure data

<https://gitlab.com/mol-cspy/mol-cspy>

Dr. Christopher R. Taylor

The group of Prof. Graeme Day
University of Southampton, UK

PSDI Roadshow, Southampton
7 July 2025

Crystal structure prediction

Given just a 2D molecular diagram, can we predict the most likely crystalline form(s) of a molecule and their properties?

Crystal structure **affects material properties!**

Pharmaceuticals

Bioavailability
Tabletability
Shelf stability

Organic electronics

Charge transport
Optical properties

Porous materials

Porosity
Stability
Selectivity

Energetic materials

Impact sensitivity
Mechanical behaviour
P/T stability

mol-CSPy: Crystal Structure Prediction in Python

Case, et al. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.*, 12(2), 910–924

A *collaboratively-developed* package to automate, parallelise, and manage the **CSP workflow**

Molecular information

- Automates calculation of 3D molecular conformations and properties required

Crystal structure generation

- Quasi-randomly generates** thousands of unique packings using a highly-efficient and parallelised algorithm

>>10⁵ structures
(at ~50 kB each)
per molecule

Optimisation and ranking

- Rapidly **energy minimises** structures with a fast, accurate molecular mechanics (MM) model

CSP can treat over 1,000 small molecules per study

CRT, P.W.V. Butler, and G.M. Day. *Faraday Discussions*, 256, 2024

Conclusion: CSP is very powerful and scalable, but creates large quantities of crystal structure data and properties, and this is accelerating, even as the larger dataset becomes more valuable (e.g. ML/AI training).

Towards a central database of CSP information

- Each published CSP investigation can now routinely generate **10 GB to >1 TB of data**
 - Predicted crystal structures, energies, calculated properties, metadata...
- We are now **making more use of both the size and scope of this data**:
 - improved interatomic potentials using ML (Taylor *et al*, *Faraday Discuss.*, 2024)
 - property prediction using neural networks
 - evolutionary algorithms for exploring chemical space (Johal and Day, DOI: 10.26434/chemrxiv-2025-v8692)
- We are working with the Research Software Group to develop a **centralised, unified database of our CSP data** as well as **related tools** for interfacing and exploring.
 - Alpha deployed, with internal testing underway
- Make our CSP data more **FAIR** by standardising location, format, and method of interaction
 - Allow **programmatic access** via APIs, autonomous access
 - Adhere to (and drive) **developing standards** in CSP research
 - Empower the **materials discovery** community
 - Open to exploring interaction and access **via PSDI**

Acknowledgments

Prof. Graeme M. Day
and
The Day Group

Dr. Stephen Pooley and the RSG

The organisers of the PSDI
Roadshow

“mol-cspy” on GitLab

European Research Council
Established by the European Commission

This project has received funding from the **European Research Council (ERC)** under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No. **856405**)

Via our membership of the UK’s HEC Materials Chemistry Consortium, which is funded by EPSRC (EP/X035859), this work used the ARCHER2 UK National Supercomputing Service (<http://www.archer2.ac.uk>).

Data management and FAIR Standards – A Crystallographers Perspective

Simon Coles.

The beginnings... 1950's/60's...

'The collective use of data would lead to the discovery of new knowledge which transcends the results of individual experiments.'
J.D. Bernal 1948

Crystal structure databases – disciplinary coverage

- Cambridge Structural Database
 - organic and metal-organic compounds
 - **>1,350,000 structures**
- Inorganic Crystal Structure Database
 - inorganic compounds
 - **300,000 structures**
- Protein Data Bank
 - biological macromolecules
 - **210,000 structures**

CCDC

1965

 FIZ KARLSRUHE
NIST

1978

WORLDWIDE
 PDB
PROTEIN DATA BANK

1971

The rise of the machines

The power of scaling up

A need for standardisation

- CIF Crystallographic Information File 1990
- “Archiving and information interchange standard for crystallographic and related structural science data”
- “Restricted-syntax implementation of the general Self-Defining Text Archival and Retrieval (STAR) File format”
- “Names and attributes of standard data items are defined in publicly available data dictionaries”
- “Under the authority of an IUCr Committee (COMCIFS)”

Acta Cryst. (1991). **A47**, 655–685

International Union of Crystallography

Commission on Crystallographic Data

Commission on Journals

Working Party on Crystallographic Information

**The Crystallographic Information File (CIF): a New Standard
Archive File for Crystallography***

BY SYDNEY R. HALL

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(Received 8 April 1991; accepted 28 June 1991)

Abstract

The specification of a new standard Crystallographic Information File (CIF) is described. Its development is based on the Self-Defining Text Archive and Retrieval (STAR) procedure [Hall (1991), *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.* **31**, 326–333]. The CIF is a general, flexible and easily extensible free-format archive file; it is human and machine readable and can be edited by a simple text editor. The CIF is designed for the electronic transmission of crystallographic data between individual laboratories, journals and databases: it has been adopted by the International Union of Crystallography as the recommended medium for this purpose. The file consists of data names and data items, together with a loop facility for repeated items. The

Introduction

There is an increasing need in many branches of science for a uniform but flexible method of archiving and exchanging data in electronic form. Rapid advances in computer technology, coupled with the expansion of local, national and international networks, have fuelled the need for such a facility. The variety and relative inflexibility of existing data exchange formats have inhibited their effective use. This is true even in fields where the basic data requirements are well defined. Problems of data exchange are further exacerbated if the number and nature of data types change rapidly and continuously. Under these conditions specialized and local file formats have proliferated. This diversity was tolerable when electronic data transfer was infrequent, or when data processing speeds required file formats finely tuned to specific applications.

The role of the International Union of Crystallography

- Governance & standards development...

COMMITTEE FOR THE MAINTENANCE OF THE CIF STANDARD (COMCIFS)

The Committee for the Maintenance of the CIF Standard oversees the development of the Crystallographic Information Framework and reports to the Executive Committee of the IUCr.

COMCIFS was established at the 16th IUCr Congress in Beijing in 1993. It supervises the orderly development of software systems to use CIF, and is responsible for the commissioning and management of dictionaries of subject-specific data items. Each dictionary has a dedicated Working Group (prior to initial acceptance) or Management Group (when the dictionary has been accepted by COMCIFS). These groups have autonomy to work within their relevant communities to develop or maintain the dictionaries.

Drafts are submitted to COMCIFS for technical validation and ultimately for approval. The COMCIFS Chair acts as coordinator of different dictionary activities.

Formal mechanisms (e.g. a name space register) exist to allow informal or private dictionary development. Private dictionaries can serve many useful purposes:

- during initial development of a new topic area
- to test new areas or ideas
- for use in non-crystallographic communities that do not report to IUCr
- to implement reasonable extensions during the sometimes lengthy COMCIFS review and approval process

Data items developed under private data names can be integrated with "official" dictionaries through an aliasing mechanism. Aliasing also allows interoperability of DDL 1- and DDL2-based applications.

- › Terms of reference
- › Current membership
- › Statement of policy
- › COMCIFS discussion list
- › Discussion List of the Core Dictionary Maintenance Group
- › Information Management Symposium 2013
- › Information Management Workshop 2013
- › Dictionary Writing Workshop 2017
- › Crystallographic Information Fiesta 2019
- › Dictionary Writing Workshop 2023
- › COMCIFS GitHub page

**INTERNATIONAL TABLES
FOR CRYSTALLOGRAPHY**

VOLUME G: DEFINITION AND

CIF DICTIONARIES

CIF dictionaries provide a formal taxonomy of crystallographic terms and ideas. Dictionary entries are constructed in a structured machine-readable manner that facilitates validation and structuring of data. New entries may be devised for public or private dictionaries. A candidate data-name definition should fulfil the following conditions: (i) describe a specific and well defined concept: precision of definition is essential for an effective interchange mechanism; (ii) have appropriate granularity: data names can define a very small piece of information (a standard uncertainty on a particular physical measurable) or a very large amount (the text of a scientific paper); (iii) have well defined relationships with other data items (through its assigned category membership and parent/child links); (iv) constraints on the data type and permissible values should be provided where applicable; (v) the name chosen should be globally unique; this is achieved through monitoring of names in public dictionaries by a regulatory committee (COMCIFS) and by registering of prefix strings for exclusive use in local dictionaries.

See also:

McMahon, B. (2006). *General considerations when defining a CIF data item*. *International Tables for Crystallography*, Vol. G. *Definition and exchange of crystallographic data*, 1st online ed., ch. 3.1, pp. 73-91. Chester: International Union of Crystallography. [doi: 10.1107/97809553602060000733]

CURRENT CIF DICTIONARIES

The CIF dictionaries listed below belong to a single namespace. They include dictionaries that are maintained by COMCIFS, as well as dictionaries maintained by other trusted organisations. A machine-readable register of CIF dictionaries maintained by the IUCr is **available**.

DESCRIPTORS FOR DIFFRACTION TECHNIQUES AND SMALL-MOLECULE, INORGANIC AND OTHER SMALL-UNIT-CELL STRUCTURES

- › Search for CIF data name
- › Core CIF dictionary
- › Restraints dictionary
- › Powder CIF dictionary
- › Modulated structures CIF dictionary
- › Electron density CIF dictionary
- › Twinning CIF dictionary
- › Macromolecular CIF dictionary
- › Image CIF dictionary
- › Symmetry CIF dictionary
- › Magnetic CIF dictionary
- › Topology CIF dictionary

**INTERNATIONAL TABLES
FOR CRYSTALLOGRAPHY**

VOLUME G: DEFINITION AND
EXCHANGE OF CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC
DATA

First online edition (2006)

The role of the International Union of Crystallography

- Oversight, horizon scanning, informing...CommDat
- Publishing, Databases, raw data, CODATA

COMMITTEE ON DATA (COMM DAT)

- Public discussion forum
- Workshop at ECM-32, Vienna: August 18 2019
- Crystallographic Information Fiesta 2019, Naples: August 29 - September 3, 2019
- Workshop on *When should small molecule crystallographers publish raw diffraction data?* at IUCr XXV, Prague: August 11-12 2021
- Workshop on *MX raw image data and metadata, formats and validation* at IUCr XXV, Prague: August 14 2021
- Workshop on *Raw diffraction data reuse: the good, the bad and the challenging* at IUCr XXVI, Melbourne: August 22 2023

The **Committee on Data** was established by the IUCr Executive Committee at its meeting in Denver in July 2016. The Committee on Data (CommDat) will work with the IUCr's Commissions, including the Commission on Journals, having a coordinating and advisory role regarding data. CommDat will report directly to the IUCr's Executive Committee and will subsume the functions of the Diffraction Data Deposition Working Group, which will cease to exist as a separate entity from the time of the IUCr Congress in Hyderabad in August 2017, and will continue the data-related interests of the now discontinued Committee on Crystallographic Databases and Committee on Electronic, Publishing, Dissemination and Storage of Information. It will exist alongside, and have a formal relationship with, the Committee for the Maintenance of the CIF Standard (COMCIFS), which will continue with its technical brief to manage the CIF standard, at least during the current period of active development of the CIF specification and dictionaries.

INTERNATIONAL UNION OF CRYSTALLOGRAPHY

advisory committees > committee on data

» Meeting Support Committee

» Committee on Data (CommDat)

» Committee for the Maintenance of the CIF Standard (COMCIFS)

» IUCr/OUP Book Series

» Gender Equity and Diversity Committee

» Outreach Committee

COMMITTEE ON DATA (COMM DAT)

CommDat online information

The Committee on Data was established by the IUCr Executive Committee at its meeting in Denver in July 2016. The Committee on Data (CommDat) will work with the IUCr's Commissions, including the Commission on Journals, having a coordinating and advisory role regarding data. CommDat will report directly to the IUCr's Executive Committee and will subsume the functions of the **Diffraction Data Deposition Working Group**, which will cease to exist as a separate entity from the time of the IUCr Congress in Hyderabad in August 2017, and will continue the data-related interests of the now discontinued **Committee on Crystallographic Databases** and **Committee on Electronic, Publishing, Dissemination and Storage of Information**. It will exist alongside, and have a formal relationship with, the Committee for the Maintenance of the CIF Standard (COMCIFS), which will continue with its technical brief to manage the CIF standard, at least during the current period of active development of the CIF specification and dictionaries.

MEMBERSHIP

- S. Coles (Chair, UK)
- H.J. Bernstein (USA)
- A. Brink (South Africa)
- I. Bruno (UK)
- S. Coles (UK)
- K. Dziubek (Austria)
- A. Goetz (France)
- S. Kabekkodu (USA)
- L.M.J. Kroon-Batenburg (The Netherlands)
- G. Kurisu (Japan)
- W. Minor (USA)
- S. Storm (Germany)
- L. Van Meervelt (Belgium)
- J. Hester (Australia) (COMCIFS liaison)

CONSULTANTS

Freeform

Crystallographic Information Framework

- 1990-2000(ish) – “standard file structure for the archiving and distribution of crystallographic information”

The acronym CIF is used both for the *Crystallographic Information File*, the data exchange standard file format of Hall, Allen & Brown (1991) (see [Documentation](#)), and for the *Crystallographic Information Framework*, a broader system of exchange protocols based on data dictionaries and relational rules expressible in different machine-readable manifestations, including, but not restricted to, Crystallographic Information File and XML.

CIF was developed by the IUCr Working Party on Crystallographic Information in an effort sponsored by the IUCr Commission on Crystallographic Data and the IUCr Commission on Journals, and was adopted in 1990 as a standard file structure for the archiving and distribution of crystallographic information. It is now well established and is in regular use for reporting crystal structure determinations to *Acta Crystallographica* and other journals. It is often cited as a model example of integrating data and textual information for data-centric scientific communication. In 2006 the importance of CIF and the value of its accompanying web-based service for the validation of structural data, *checkCIF*, were

- 2000(ish) onwards
- “model example of integrating data and textual information for data-centric scientific communication”
- easily accessible
- served to make critical crystallographic data more consistently reliable
- accessible at all stages of the information chain, from authors, reviewers and editors through to readers and researchers

Supporting data to knowledge

Full stakeholder buy-in across the whole data lifecycle

Small molecule crystallography ‘Quality Framework’

The basis of FAIR Crystallography

- >100 years of instrumentation development
 - >50 years of building highly valuable and curated results databases
 - >40 years of trusted common refinement processes
 - >30 years of agreed and maintained standards
 - >20 years of validation tools
- Well understood statistics for the suitability of a dataset and the fit of a model
- New methods are stretching this framework
- Additional approaches required

Drivers for better data management are growing...fast...

- More challenging samples
- More challenging experiments
 - Dynamic crystallography (High Pressure, Gas Cell, Laser Excitation)
- New structure determination methods
 - e.g. NMR Crystallography, Electron Diffraction, Crystal Sponge
- New structure refinement methods
 - e.g. Quantum Crystallography, Dynamical refinement
- New Structure analysis methods
 - e.g. Quantum Crystallography

Data should be fit for purpose...

- Original purpose of structure determination
 - What have I made?
 - What is the reaction by-product?
 - How has my structure changed?
 - How does this material manifest these properties?
 - What are the driving forces behind structure formation, how do I control them?
- How others will reuse the results
 - Do chemicals like this exist (connectivity)
 - Starting point for follow on calculations (conformation)
 - Highly accurate structural features (precise structure)

But the world is changing again...

- PSDI: The opportunity to aggregate crystallographic data directly with other data...
- The rise of AI/ML...
- The opportunity to integrate crystallographic data directly with other data...and then reason/process across it
- >>> Learn, and then predict, structure - property relationships?
- >>> Multi-modal studies without the need for expensive instrumentation?
- The key (power?) lies in [AI ready] FAIR data...

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Keys to success...

- Coherent community
- Instrument data
- Data standards
- Automated validation
- Governing body
- Connected information chain
- Collections that can drive new science

- Open data, open software, open standards, open minded...

YOUR QUESTIONS

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Balancing Trust and Verification

Data auditing as the backbone of reliable chemistry data

8th July 2025
Dr Matthew Partridge

psdi.ac.uk

Building Data Collections

- ▶ Develop robust methods to build, store, manage, and export diverse physical chemistry data collections
- ▶ Aggregate and standardise data from various sources, including institutional repositories, and publications
- ▶ Provide datasets for identified applications from aggregated data collection
- ▶ Provide case studies on these methodologies

Building Data Collections

- ▶ Develop robust methods to build, store, manage, and export diverse physical chemistry data collections
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- ▶ Provide case studies on these methodologies

Physical Chemistry Properties Data Collection

Physical Chemistry Properties Data Collection

Cherqaoui1994
Kim2024

BioQuest
WikiData

Bergstrom2003
Williams2015

Sander2023

DDB2023
IUPAC

BigSolDB
SolProp
Boobier2020
Delaney2004
Llompart2024
Lowe2023
Meng2022

Our data auditing

- ▶ Aim is to make the collection **reliable, traceable, usable, and consistent**
- ▶ To do this we need to answer the following questions
 - ▶ What is the source of this data?
 - ▶ Is the data complete and understood?
 - ▶ Can we use this data?

Auditing is NOT peer review

What is the source of this data?

Cherqaoui1994

[View Article Online / Journal Homepage / Table of Contents for this issue](#)

J. CHEM. SOC. FARADAY TRANS., 1994, 90(1), 97-102

97

Use of a Neural Network to determine the Boiling Point of Alkanes

Driss Cherqaoui and Didier Villemin*

Ecole Nationale Supérieure d'Ingénieurs de Caen (E.N.S.I. de Caen), I.S.M.R.A., U.R.A. 480 CNRS, 6 boulevard du Maréchal Juin, 14050 Caen Cedex, France

Back-propagation neural networks (NNs) are useful for the study of quantitative structure-activity relationships or structure-property correlations. Models of relationships between structure and boiling point (bp) of 150 alkanes were constructed by means of a multilayer neural network (NN) using the back-propagation algorithm. The results of our NN were compared with those of other models from the literature, and found to be better. The boiling points of the 150 alkanes were then predicted by removing 15 compounds (test set) and using the 135 other molecules as a training set. Using the same process, all the compounds in the data bank were then predicted in groups of 15 compounds. The results obtained were satisfying.

Quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPRs) quantify the connection between the structure and the properties of molecules and allow the prediction of properties from structural parameters. We report herein one of the first approaches of QSPR using a neural network (NN). In this study, the structure-property (bp) correlation of the first 150 alkanes¹ has been made with an NN.

The ability to adapt and generalize an NN makes it of great possible value when applied to chemistry.^{2,3} NNs have attracted the attention of chemists who have found that the characteristics of these networks are adapted to data processing in which the relationship between a cause and its effects cannot be exactly defined. NMR, IR, mass spectrometry and other processes of spectroscopy provide spectra with which chemical compounds have to correspond. The existing computer tools search data bases and provide responses

We have chosen to test the NN approach on hydrocarbon molecules, because these molecules are simple, easy to code, and do not have polarised atoms or intermolecular bonds. The boiling points of hydrocarbons depend upon molecular shape and vary regularly within a series of homologous compounds. It is a typical feature of organic compounds. The bps of alkanes have been predicted many times¹⁷⁻²⁵ and consequently it is easy to compare the NN approach with other approaches described in the literature.

Methods

Theory

NN²⁶ is a computer-based system derived from a simplified concept of the brain in which a number of nodes, called the processing elements, are interconnected in a net-like struc-

Experiment

The alkanes and their bps (Table 1) were taken from Mihalic *et al.*²⁰ In the present study the NN needed an input pattern corresponding to the molecule's structure and an output

What is the source of this data?

28

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Comparative Study of Molecular Descriptors Derived from the Distance Matrix

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A comparative study of 10 distance indices derived from the distance matrix either in the graph-theoretical (topological) form or in the geometric (topographic) form is carried out. They are partitioned into five topological indices and five topographic indices. The adjective topological or topographic indicates which matrix each family of distance indices has originated from. All five topological indices have been known in the literature, while four out of five topographic indices are introduced in this work. Only the 3-D Wiener number has been proposed earlier. Most of distance indices are found to be intercorrelated, i.e., they contain similar structural information. Only 2-J and 3-J indices did not intercorrelate with any other distance index but themselves. The three most accurate structure-property models for predicting boiling points of alkanes are based on the connectivity index χ , its variant χ' ($= N\chi$), and on the topological distance index 2-TI. It is unclear at present why the 3-D distance indices have produced inferior structure-boiling point models in comparison with models based on the 2-D distance indices and connectivity indices.

INTRODUCTION

The distance matrix appears to be a convenient source for deriving molecular descriptors.¹⁻⁴ This matrix can be given

lated. In other words, we will investigate to what degree they contain the same type of constitutional and geometric information. Second, we will examine how the distance indices

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What is the source of this data?

Jan., 1947 STRUCTURAL DETERMINATION OF PARAFFIN BOILING POINTS 17
[CONTRIBUTION FROM DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY, BROOKLYN COLLEGE]

Structural Determination of Paraffin Boiling Points

BY HARRY WIENER¹

The boiling points of organic compounds, as well as all their physical properties, depend functionally upon the number, kind and structural arrangement of the atoms in the molecule. Within a group of isomers, both the number and the kind of atoms are constant, and variations in physical properties are due to changes in structural interrelationships alone. The study of the effect of pure structural variation upon the boiling point of the paraffins may be expected to be of some theoretical interest. It will be shown in this paper that satisfactory results can readily be obtained by this approach.

The boiling points of the paraffins are given by the linear formula

$$t_b = aw + bp + c \quad (1)$$

where a , b and c are constants for a given isomeric group, and p and w are structural variables defined below.

The polarity number p is defined as the number of pairs of carbon atoms which are separated by three carbon-carbon bonds. *E.g.*, for 2,3-dimethylpentane

$C_1-C_2-C_3-C_4-C_5$ Pairs 3 bonds apart: C_1C_4 , C_1

of least squares, to the selected boiling point data for the thirty-seven paraffins from C_4H_{10} to $C_{14}H_{30}$ in the tables of the American Petroleum Institute Research Project 44.³

The resulting equation is

$$\Delta t = \frac{0.8}{n^2} \Delta w + 5.5 \Delta p \quad (4)$$

which is the form used in this paper.

The change in notation introduced by equation (2) is useful not only because of the resulting simplification, but also because it refers the boiling points of the branched isomers to the boiling points of the normal paraffins, which throughout the series have been much more intensively and accurately determined and correlated. In particular, Egloff's equation⁴:

$$t_b = 745.42 \log (u + 4.4) - 689.4 \quad (5)$$

reproduces the data to within their experimental limits. Table I gives the reference values for the normal paraffins from n -butane to n -dodecane. For normal paraffins, the structural variables are given by

selected boiling point values are given in the A.P.I. tables,³ and from which data the two empirical constants of equation (4) were evaluated.

(3) American Petroleum Institute Research Project 44 at the National Bureau of Standards. Selected values of Physical and Thermodynamical Properties of Hydrocarbons. Tables No. 1a, 2a, 3a and 4a, dated June 30, 1945.

What is the source of this data?

SELECTED VALUES OF PROPERTIES OF HYDROCARBONS
American Petroleum Institute Research Project 44
National Bureau of Standards Washington, D. C.

TABLE 1a-E - PARAFFINS, C₁ to C₅
BOILING POINT, dt/dp, REFRACTIVE INDEX, DENSITY, AND FREEZING POINT
June 30, 1945

Compound	Formula	Boiling Point	dt/dp	Refractive Index		Density		Freezing Point	
		29.921 in. Hg ^a	29.921 in. Hg ^a	66°F	70°F	60°F	60°F	60°F	60°F
		t_b	deg F/in. Hg	n_D	n_D	d_4^{20}	d_4^{20}	t_f	t_f
Methane	CH ₄	-258.68	0.732	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ethane	C ₂ H ₆	-127.53	1.116	-	-	-	-	-	-
Propane	C ₃ H ₈	-43.73	1.362	-	-	-	-	-	-
n-Butane	C ₄ H ₁₀	31.10	1.586	-	-	-	-	-	-
2-Methylpropane (isobutane)	"	10.49	1.541	-	-	35.12 ^e	34.78 ^e	34.40 ^e	4.696 ^e
n-Pentane	C ₅ H ₁₂	96.93	1.765	1.35748	1.35475	39.363	39.094	38.791	5.2621
2-Methylbutane (isopentane)	"	82.14	1.742	1.35373	1.35088	38.964	38.684	38.369	5.2088
2,2-Dimethylpropane (neopentane)	"	49.10	1.669	-	-	-	-	-	5.1713

^a 1 atm = 29.921 in. Hg. ^b For air-saturated hydrocarbon in the liquid state at one atmosphere, unless otherwise indicated.
^c For the sodium D line, for which the wave length is taken to be 5892.6 Ångstrom units, which is the intensity-weighted mean of the wave lengths of the D₁ and D₂ lines. ^d The density of water at 60°F (15.556°C) is taken as 0.99904 g/ml. ^e At saturation pressure.
^f For air-saturated hydrocarbon at one atmosphere, unless otherwise indicated. ^g Triple point.

Compound	API value (°C)	Value in data set (°C)
Methane	-161.49	-164
Ethane	-88.6	Missing
Propane	-42.1	-42.1
n-Butane	-0.5	-0.5

What is the source of this data?

- ▶ BigSolDB
- ▶ SolProp
- ▶ Boobier2020
- ▶ Delaney2004
- ▶ Llompert2024
- ▶ Lowe2023
- ▶ Meng2022

Is the data complete & understood?

- ▶ Details matter
- ▶ Every subject has specific details
- ▶ Not always possible to capture everything but planning is critical
- ▶ Key considerations
 - ▶ Experimental conditions
 - ▶ Outliers
 - ▶ Impossible values
 - ▶ Accidental replicates
 - ▶ Missing values

Is the data complete & understood?

Is the data complete & understood?

Is the data complete & understood?

Can we use this data?

- ▶ Being online doesn't automatically give you free use
- ▶ Academic fair use and republication are very different things
- ▶ Older (pre-2000) work rarely has licencing information
- ▶ Creative Commons zero (CC0) is the best to look for
- ▶ When in doubt, get consent from originating author
- ▶ **Always** provide citations

Summary

- ▶ There is a difference between trust and verification
- ▶ Always verify
 - ▶ The source
 - ▶ The data
 - ▶ The usage
- ▶ Not every data set has a simple answers and there is some judgement needed
- ▶ If in doubt, keep detailed records and notes!
- ▶ Just like the source data the choices behind a collection should be verifiable

Thank-you, and questions

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National
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Centre

Oceanographic Data Management

Richenda Houseago-Stokes

British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC)

BODC is the UK National Marine Data Centre

It is a national facility for looking after and distributing data from the marine environment.

BODC has a range of roles and responsibilities including:

- The National Oceanographic Database
- UK Tide Gauge Network
- The designated marine data centre for the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)
- An accredited Data Archive Centre (DAC) within the Marine Environmental Data and Information Network (MEDIN)
- Project data management

About the NERC Environmental Data Service

For scientific data spanning all environmental science domains.
A network of distributed data centres, with domain specific expertise

British Oceanographic Data Centre
Marine

Centre for Environmental Data Analysis
Atmospheric, Earth Observation, and
Solar and Space Physics

Environmental Information Data Centre
Terrestrial and Freshwater

National Geoscience Data Centre
Geoscience

UK Polar Data Centre
Polar and Cryosphere

WHO USES OUR DATA?

Public

150,000

distinct users supported

Industry

63% of our users are from outside academic research

Government Agencies

Education

Research

64% of our users are from outside the UK

DATA ACCESS

16,060

DATASETS AVAILABLE via the EDS data catalogue service

stored in over 25PB OF DATA

3,764 CITATIONS from 1,147 NERC DATASETS

8+ million

DOWNLOADS

From the NERC vocabulary server

4+ million

DATA ACCESS REQUESTS

Through the borehole access API

624 DOI s ISSUED This year

Out of 4,442 TOTAL DOIs

USER ENGAGEMENT

300

ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES

Over 120 of those having wide reach and influence

21 Research Data Management training events delivered by our staff to

~300 people

Our staff were involved in

18

peer reviewed publications

3,873

USER QUERIES RESOLVED

Research Data Management Lifecycle

The data life cycle is the sequence of stages that data goes through from its initial generation through its archival and reuse.

- 1) Data Management planning
- 2) Data collection and capture, collection and analysis
- 3) Data storage and archiving, sharing and publishing
- 4) Data cataloguing, discovery and reuse

Data Management Planning

- A DMP is a living document, which can be updated throughout the research project as needed.
- Important for agreeing approach with project members what happens to the data during and after the project life time.

DMP

1. Project description
2. Roles and responsibilities
3. Reusing data
4. Creating and collecting data
5. Processing and analysing data
6. Data preservation
7. Licensing and ethics

The EDS Data Management Plan

British
Oceanographic
Data Centre

Questionnaire Preview Documents Settings

View Import replies

TODOs Comments 1 Version history

Current phase
During the grant

Chapters

- I. Grant information 3
- II. Re-using data 6
- III. Creating and coll... 6
- IV. Processing and a... 1
- V. Preserving and s... 4**
- VI. Communications... 1

V. Preserving and sharing data

This section helps you consider research data publication and long term archiving.

V.1 Is there a funder requirement that any of your data are deposited with a long term repository?

BODC EDS

Mandatory: *During the grant*

External links: [Read more: Policies and standards affecting research data management](#)

a. No DMP Practice 0%

b. Yes DMP Practice 100%

c. Not applicable, no data being generated

Clear answer

Answered over 1 year ago by Richenda Houseago-Stokes.

V.1.b.1 Estimate the volume of data you are likely to be depositing with a repository

EDS

Check with the repository you are using if they have a have a limit to the volume of data that can be deposited, or if depositing higher volumes of data that need to be budgeted for.

Mandatory: *During the grant*

a. Total data volume is > 1 TB

b. Data volume is > 100 GB but < 1 TB so might cause an issue with storage or costs

5.1 Datasets this grant plans to create

Environmental Datasets

Title	Description	Format	License	Size	IPR	Is data derived?	Date Generated	Preservation Plan	Deposit Date	Embargo Date	Repository	Person Responsible
CTD	temp. sal, cond We are calibrating measurements. Information not supplied. We are not using any other quality processes.	NetCDF (nc)	freely available with obligation to quote the source (OGL or CC-BY licence)	Less than 10GB	noc	No	2024-02-28	Sent to a repository.	2024-02-28	2024-02-27	British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC)	me

Information Products

No information products will be created by this grant.

What Is FAIR Data?

- Open science is not just about disclosure
- Research assets must also be **FAIR**

Can your data be found easily by humans and machines?

Once it is found, is your data easy to access and download?

Is your data easy to integrate with other data, workflows, and applications?

Does your dataset have all the correct metadata so that it can be reused in the future?

Making Your Data FAIR

- Self assessment tools
 - determine FAIRness of your data set
 - Help to improve the FAIRness of your data (where necessary)
 - <https://www.ands.org.au/working-with-data/fairdata/fair-data-self-assessment-tool>
- Trusted repositories
 - <https://repositoryfinder.datacite.org/>
- Resources
 - <https://www.dtls.nl/fair-data/fair-data/>
 - <https://fairsharing.org/>
 - <https://www.ands.org.au/working-with-data/fairdata/training>

What Is MEDIN?

National framework for managing UK marine data

Long-term, open partnership, established 2008

Funded by 16 sponsors

Over 60 partners

Hosted at the National Oceanography Centre

'measure once, use many times'

Group of organisations, tools and resources that make it easier to share UK marine data

A Single Place To “Find” UK Marine Data

- MEDIN discovery metadata portal
<https://portal.medin.org.uk/portal/start.php>
- The hub for UK marine data
- Over 18,900 datasets from 600 organisations
- ‘How to find marine data’ video:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8YKS_5AThkg

The screenshot shows the MEDIN portal search interface. On the left is a map of the UK with a grid overlay. The main content area is titled 'MEDIN' and 'Search for marine data across UK organisations'. It includes a 'Welcome to the MEDIN portal' message, a 'Need help?' link, and a 'SEARCH' section with a 'Free search' input field, 'Date' (From/To), 'Season of Interest' dropdown, and 'Geographical bounding box' (North, West, East, South) fields. There is a checkbox for 'Search item completely within bounding box' and a 'Data theme' dropdown. A 'SEARCH PARAMETERS' section is partially visible at the bottom. On the right, there is a 'DATA COLLECTIONS' section with buttons for UKHO, DASSH, Cefas, TCE, BODC, MDSG, NRW, and BGS. Below that is an 'ICES rectangles search' section.

A Network Of Accredited Data Archive Centres

Why visit a data centre?

Marine Discovery Metadata Standard

British
Oceanographic
Data Centre

UK Marine Standard:

UK Standard:
GEMINI2

European Standard:
INSPIRE Directive

International Standard:
ISO19115

Interoperable

Standard

Controlled
vocabularies

Tools to ensure data are reusable

MEDIN Data Guidelines

list of information that should be collected with your data to ensure they can be re-used in the future.

Tailored to 30 different methods/data types

Guidelines

Community derived
and supported

R_{eusable}

MEDIN Training And Resources

Guides and tutorials for using MEDIN resources;
@MEDIN_marine

Marine data management, governance and the MEDIN toolset – Free online workshops:

- Enhance Data Quality & Accessibility by equipping participants with skills to create well-documented, discoverable, and reusable marine datasets.
- Encourage consistent use of metadata standards (e.g. ISO 19115, INSPIRE), enabling seamless data sharing across organisations.
- Empower marine professionals with practical knowledge and tools to manage and publish data effectively.

Active social media
@MEDIN_marine

Questions The EDS Asks When Looking For A Data Repository

- Is the repository a sustainable service ?
 - look for evidence of mid- to long-term funding
- Does the repository have an open access metadata catalogue?
- Does the data catalogue adhere to recognisable metadata standards?
- Does the repository require data to be stored in non-proprietary, documented and supported formats?
- Does the repository have any certification?
- Does the funding call require use of a specific repository?

Considerations when using an institutional repository

- If you are using an institutional repository
 - How can you ensure your data are found?
 - Are any data aggregation services available to you?
- If building a repository, what is available in the community?
 - Consider if there are already any standards/common vocabularies etc. available

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Thank you for listening
Any questions?

noc.ac.uk, bodc.ac.uk, medin.org.uk

Data stewardship: the role of technicians/RTPs

Dr Louise Saul

8th July 2025

PSDI/DCC roadshow @
University of Southampton

- The role of technicians/RTPs in the research workflow
- Points at which technicians/RTPs can support in data curation and management
- Creating opportunities for collaboration and discussion

The essential role of technicians

- Role of technicians in the 17th Century (1989 – The Invisible Technician, Steve Shapin) but technicians have been recorded since 700 AD

“[...] It should be pointed out that a central part of the tasks undertaken by technicians is directed towards making machines run smoothly, so that the creation* of usable data is unproblematic.”

- Illiffe, 2008 (* I take issue with this...)

- Technician Commitment (Vere, 2022)

The Technician Commitment

Visibility

Sustainability

Recognition

Career
Development

What sorts of responsibilities do technicians/RTPs have?

Facilities
management

Training and
support

In research
groups

Expertise in a
specific
technique

Data Stewardship

Awareness of organisational culture

Maintain quality of data

Be aware of industry standards

Strategic thinking

Communicate with users

Knowledge of data collection and storage

Technician/RTP involvement in the research data lifecycle?

Input of Technicians/RTPs into data management/curation

- File types and software requirements
- Proprietary restrictions/IP
- Data processing
- Methods sections
- Time points and conditions
- Storage requirements and data size
- Support with downstream data use
- How to make that data open
- Not an exhaustive list!

Challenges faced

- For appropriate and efficient data back-up procedures (often need to back up hundreds of files a day with lack of infrastructure)
- Security of data
- Remote access to data for multi-partner projects
- Time allocation for data stewardship and recognition in workload

Variability within the role

Contract types

Grade

Freedom to engage

Collaborations and discussion

- Engage with technicians/RTPs as soon as possible in the project
- Ensure that you're aware of the remit and experience of technical staff
- Discuss costs for management and storage of data
- Is the role of data stewardship recognised?
- Is the role of data stewardship for technicians/RTPs supported?

Moving forward

Data practices
CPD designed for
technicians

Continued
work with the
Technician
Commitment

Promote visibility by
seeking input from
technicians in
institutional activities

- Agnes Michalek and Nic Pratt
- Julie Herniman
- Simon Hettrick
- Sami Pearman-Kanza

Thank you!

